

FINAL REPORT

SPOKE 1: MOUNTAIN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM

PROJECT NAME: Decarbonization and Optimization of Local Off-grid Mountain huts energy system through Green Hydrogen Technology

The Final Report relates to the scientific activities carried out and the results achieved within the project funded through the Young Researcher Call for Proposals: it must provide a comprehensive description of the project results, with specific reference to the project activities carried out, the progress made and the achievement of the milestones and targets set out in the approved project.

The Final Report is submitted by the PI (principal investigator) and is evaluated by the Scientific Committee, in accordance with the provisions of the aforementioned Call for Proposals.

The Final Report must underscore these aspects:

- the final objectives achieved and set out in the project submitted for evaluation, as well as any deviations from the established objectives and the reasons for such deviations;
- any deviations between the approved Economic and Financial Plan and the reported costs, that must be justified.

PROJECT DETAILS	
Spoke	1 – Mountain Innovation Ecosystem
PROJECT ACRONYM	DOLOMIGH ₂ T
PI – Principal Investigator - University	Carlo Caligiuri
Starting date:	
Duration:	
Ending date:	31.12.2024
Other participants - university	SAMUEL POLLACHINI

Annexes:

Possible annex	
Possible annex	

Date: -----

PI signature: -----

1. Technical and scientific results of the project

1.1. Description of the final results achieved

Maximum two pages.

Images and diagrams may be attached at the end of the report. Indicate whether the expected results were achieved, explaining and quantifying any deviations.

Describe the expected and actual results of the project in qualitative terms.

Energy production in Alpine and mountain environments is strongly constrained by extreme seasonality, harsh weather conditions, and geographical isolation. These factors cause large variability in renewable energy availability and lead to a continued reliance on diesel generators. In particular, solar irradiation can vary by up to 85% between summer and winter, while wind resources are often intermittent, making year-round renewable energy supply particularly challenging.

The DOLMIGH2T project proposed hydrogen technology as a key enabler for resilient, carbon-neutral energy systems in off-grid mountain applications. Excess renewable energy generated during summer periods is used to produce green hydrogen via electrolysis. This hydrogen is then stored and converted back into electricity during winter, when renewable production is limited. In this way, hydrogen provides long-term seasonal energy storage, overcoming the intrinsic limitations of conventional battery-based solutions.

The project aimed to develop and validate tailored zero-carbon energy solutions for Alpine environments by replicating typical energy conditions of the North-East Italian Alpine (NEST) region in a controlled laboratory setting. This approach combined hardware adaptation with the development of innovative energy management software. DOLMIGH2T directly addressed the three research themes of Spoke 1 by promoting energy autonomy (RT3), improving system resilience and year-round energy availability (RT2), and enhancing safety, comfort, and sustainability in remote mountain areas (RT1).

The main outcome of the project was the realization of a state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure, named HUT2LAB, developed around two main pillars:

Renewable Energy Source Simulation Unit (RESim).

This unit consists of a programmable power supply capable of accurately reproducing renewable energy conditions typical of Alpine locations. General-purpose hardware was adapted to meet the specific requirements of the project, enabling the simulation of solar and wind energy availability under different seasonal, meteorological, and geographical scenarios representative of the NEST region.

Integrated Green Hydrogen Micro Plant (H2P).

This system replicates a complete green hydrogen energy chain by integrating three key components: hydrogen production through electrolysis, storage in pressurized cylinders, and reconversion to electricity via PEM fuel cells. The H2P enables experimental validation of hydrogen as a seasonal energy storage solution and as a flexible power source for off-grid applications. This activity demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of commercially available technologies when properly integrated and optimized for the specific constraints of mountain environments.

Highlight the starting and final TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and the main KPI (Key Performance Indicator) achieved

TRL

Starting TRL: 3–4

- At the beginning of the project, hydrogen-based seasonal storage concepts for Alpine off-grid applications were validated at an analytical and experimental proof-of-concept level. Individual components (electrolyzers, storage tanks, fuel cells, renewable generators) were commercially available, but their integration and operation under mountain-specific conditions had not been experimentally demonstrated.

Final TRL: 5

- By the end of the project, the technology reached validation in a laboratory environment. The HUT2LAB infrastructure enabled experimental demonstration of an integrated renewable–hydrogen–power system under realistic Alpine energy scenarios, including seasonal variability.

Main KPIs Achieved

- Demonstrated seasonal energy storage using green hydrogen
- Validated integrated renewable–hydrogen–fuel cell system for off-grid use
- Enabled diesel generator replacement potential in mountain huts
- Achieved near-zero operational emissions pathway

Describe the External Partners who collaborated, their contribution, and the possible synergies that may continue in the near future

The project collaborated with the external partner H2 Planet, which provided the key equipment required for the realization of the HUT2LAB laboratory infrastructure. H2 Planet's technical expertise was fundamental in the sizing of the laboratory and in the selection and configuration of the hydrogen production, storage, and conversion components. The collaboration is expected to continue beyond the project duration through active technical exchange during the experimental test phase and in follow-up activities, fostering further optimization of the system and supporting future developments and applications of hydrogen-based energy solutions for off-grid and mountain environments.

2. COMPLIANCE WITH CONDITIONALITIES AND ALL ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENTS RELATED TO THE PNRR MEASURES

2.1. DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code

Description of how the activities carried out comply with the DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code. In this regard, the reasons why the activities carried out do not cause significant harm to each of the environmental objectives are reported.

Environment	Has the DNSH principle been respected for the environmental objective? (Y/N) ³	Justifications:
1. Climate change mitigation	Y	The project promotes renewable energy and green hydrogen, reducing fossil fuel use and CO ₂ emissions.
2. Climate change adaptation	Y	Solutions are designed to ensure energy resilience under extreme seasonal and climatic conditions.
3. Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources	Y	No significant water consumption or discharge impacting water bodies is involved.
4. Transition to a circular economy, including waste reduction and recycling	Y	The project uses modular, commercially available components, supporting reuse, recyclability, and reduced waste.
5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution	Y	Replacement of diesel generators reduces air and soil pollution; no harmful emissions are generated.
6. Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystem	Y	Laboratory-based activities and reduced fuel transport minimize impacts on natural ecosystems.

2.2. Consistency with the digital constraint

Max 500 characters
<i>Describe how the activities carried out and the related expenses incurred contribute to the achievement of the digital constraint, thus promoting the digital transition and at the same time ensuring compliance with the contribution to the digital objective</i>
The project contributed to the digital objective through the development and use of digital tools for energy system simulation, monitoring, and control. Expenses supported the implementation of digital energy

³ If the activities carried out do not have an impact on the environmental objective, it is appropriate to answer "Yes", in case of "Not", enter the reasons in the "Justifications" column of the same table..

management software and a web-based GIS application for system sizing and planning. These solutions enable data-driven optimization, remote operation, and scenario analysis, promoting the digital transition while ensuring full compliance with the digital constraint requirements.

3. ECONOMICS RESULTS OF THE PROJECT

3.1. Project costs

Attach the final statement of costs incurred in connection with the project, indicating the type of cost incurred..

BUDGET	Final amount (€ - %)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
Costs for specialist consultancy services		2.597,00 €	No external specialist consultancy services were required, as all technical requirements were thoroughly investigated and developed internally.
Costs for materials, supplies and similar products	31.896,90 €	46.903,04 €	The material costs included the purchase of an AC generator, a fuel cell, an electrolyzer, hydrogen storage equipment, and web hosting services together with a management application. The total final expenditure is lower than initially planned because the Project PI terminated his activity at the end of 2024. The remaining expenditure was incurred by Dr. Jacopo C. Alberizzi within Milestone 4 of the RT3A topic of the iNEST Project.
Mission expenses		500,00 €	No mission costs were required.
Total			

BUDGET	Final amount (€ - %)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
RI -	24.497,60 € - 77%	37.224,44 - 74%	The project PI terminated his activity at the end of 2024 and only the fuel cell has been purchased.
SS -	7.399,30 € - 23%	12.775,60 - 26%	The project PI terminated his activity at the end of 2024 and only the AC generator has been purchased.
Total	31.896,90 €		

4. SUMMARY OF TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC CHANGES TO THE PROJECT (IF ANY)

Summarize the technical and financial changes that have been made to the project. Please note that, according to the call for proposals, changes must not substantially alter the objectives, results and impact of the initial project and must not lead to an increase in total expenditure. Please also specify whether the changes have an impact on the balance between the different types of expenditure.

Some financial changes have been made since the project PI terminated his activity at the end of 2024. Dr. Jacopo C. Alberizzi took responsibility of the remain purchases within the Milestone 4 of the RT3A topic of the iNEST Project.

With regard to technical aspects, no changes were made to the project objectives, expected results, or overall impact. The project concluded earlier than initially planned, on 31 December 2024, due to a change in the role of the Principal Investigator. This early termination did not affect the achievement of the core technical objectives.

The second part of the activities related to the development of the web-based GIS application (HUT2GIS) was carried out by Dr. Jacopo C. Alberizzi outside the DOLOMIGH2T project framework but within the broader activities of INEST. This ensured continuity of the research objectives without altering the scope, results, or financial structure of the original project